

Genomics of Terpene Biosynthesis in Dictyoceratid Sponges (Porifera) – What Do We (Not) Know?

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Sponges are recognized as promising sources for novel bioactive metabolites. Among them are terpenoid metabolites that constitute key biochemical defense mechanisms in several sponge taxa. Despite their significance, the genetic basis for terpenoid biosynthesis in sponges remains poorly understood. Dictyoceratida comprise demosponges well-known for their bioactive terpenoids. In this study, we explored the currently available genomic data for insights into the metabolic pathways of dictyoceratid terpenoids. We first identified prenyltransferase (PT) and terpene cyclase (TC) enzymes essential for the terpenoid biosynthetic processes in the terrestrial realm by analyzing available transcriptomic and genomic data of Dictyoceratida sponges and 10 other sponge species. All Dictyocer-

atida sponges displayed various PTs involved in either sesqui- or diterpene, steroid and carotenoid production. Additionally, it was possible to identify a potential candidate for a dictyoceratid sesterterpene PT. However, analogs of common terrestrial TCs were absent, suggesting the existence of a distinct or convergently evolved sponge-specific TC. Our study aims to contribute to the foundational understanding of terpene biosynthesis in sponges, unveiling the currently evident genetic components for terpenoid production in species not previously studied. Simultaneously, it aims to identify the known and unknown factors, as a starting point for biochemical and genetic investigations in sponge terpenoid production.

Introduction

Among the plethora of specialized metabolites produced by plants, microbes and animals, terpenoids and related natural products represent the most abundant and diverse group, with over 80,000 reported structures to date.^[1,2] Terpenes are essential for a number of biological functions, with the terpenoid biosynthetic pathway also being integral for the production of other chemical compounds of biological significance, such as steroids and carotenoids.^[3–5] While terpenoids have been mainly found in terrestrial organisms, they also make up a significant proportion of natural products of marine origin

(~8,000 i.e. >20%).^[6] Almost a third of these terpenoids are presumed to be produced by sponges (Porifera) and/or their symbionts.^[7] Terpenoids, among other metabolites, are fundamental in the biochemical defense of sponges and other sessile marine organisms.

They are used in the competition for space, for deterrence of predators, and for protection from parasites and infectious microorganisms.^[8,9] The wide range of ecological functions of these metabolites is also reflected in their multifaceted bioactivity.^[10]

Sesqui- (C_{15}) and diterpenes (C_{20}) are common sponge-derived terpenoids (e.g., in the demosponge orders Poecilosclerida, Bubarida, and Dendroceratida), while sesterterpenoids constitute a comparatively rare class of structurally diverse C_{25} terpenes, with their distribution among demosponges being particularly restricted and specific to a small number of clades (Poecilosclerida, Haplosclerida, Dictyoceratida; Figure 1).^[11] In particular, sponges of the order Dictyoceratida are the only known marine primary source of rare scalarane-type sesterterpenoids. These compounds are characterized by a unique skeleton of four *trans*-fused cyclohexane rings and include a diverse range of derivative structures and bioactive properties (Figure 2).^[12–14] Scalarane sesterterpenes from terrestrial sources are exceptionally rare and have only recently been discovered in a small number of fungi.^[15–18]

The terpenoid biosynthetic pathway generally follows the same pattern for all types of terpenes, with prenyltransferases (PTs, also known as polyprenyl synthases) synthesizing the linear terpene precursors of different lengths from the terpene building blocks isopentenyl pyrophosphate (IPP) and dimethylallyl pyrophosphate (DMAPP) through several condensation steps, up to the C_{25} sesterterpene basis geranylarnesyl

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Figure 1. Simplified phylogenetic distribution of reported terpenoid metabolites across sponge orders of the class Demospongiae (Based on Galitz et al. 2021). Asterisk indicates reports of questionable credibility.

Figure 2. Examples for structural variability of scalarane sesterterpenes: (a) basic scalarane sesterterpene skeleton; (b) scalaradial; (c) scalarin, a pentacyclic scalarane sesterterpene.

pyrophosphate (GFPP)^[19] (Scheme 1). Each of these condensation products can also serve as a respective precursor for monoterpenes (geranyl pyrophosphate (GPP)), sesqui- and triterpenes (farnesyl pyrophosphate (FPP)), and di- and tetraterpenes (geranylgeranyl pyrophosphate (GGPP)) (Scheme 1).^[20] Subsequent transformation of these linear substrates into structurally diverse terpene scaffolds is facilitated by terpene synthases (TS) and terpene cyclases (TC) in the case of cyclic terpenoids.^[21] TCs can generally be grouped into two main classes (classes I and II) according to their carbocation.^[2] Details of the still poorly understood genetic foundation of sesterterpene biosynthetic pathways in terrestrial fungi, plants, and bacteria have been explored only recently, revealing notable differences in their genetic makeup.^[22,23] In fungi, sesterterpene biosynthesis is facilitated by a bifunctional chimeric sesterterpene synthase (STS) with both a PT domain (N-terminal) and a TC domain (C-terminal). In contrast, in plants and bacteria these domains are encoded on separate genes often located in different gene clusters.^[13] In plants, a colocalized cytochrome P450 gene can provide additional complexity and diversity of the produced terpenoid metabolites.^[24,25] Earlier studies suggested that plant and fungal STS do not share a common ancestor and have evolved independently.^[26]

Research on terpenoid biosynthesis in marine taxa has made considerable progress in recent years, shedding light on the genes involved and their evolutionary history: In seaweeds, genes responsible for terpene precursor production and terpene synthesis, along with their full biosynthetic pathway, have been identified.^[27] Additionally, ancient plant-like terpenoid biosynthesis gene clusters similar to those of terrestrial

Scheme 1. Terpenoid biosynthetic pathway following the non-mevalonate (MEP) pathway. Four potential condensation steps of linear terpene precursors facilitated by the respective enzymes GPPS, FPPS, GGPPS and GFPPS (arrows, italicized), with production of final terpenoid products from the substrates catalyzed by TSs or TCs. MEP (methylerythritol-4-phosphate), GPPS (geranyl pyrophosphate synthase), FPPS (farnesyl pyrophosphate synthase), GGPPS (geranylgeranyl pyrophosphate synthase), GFPPS (geranyl-farnesyl pyrophosphate synthase).

plants and microbes have been discovered in soft corals (Octocorallia).^[28,29] Moreover, diatoms and other marine algae produce non-terpenoid neurotoxins that are synthesized by enzymes structurally and genetically similar to the terpene cyclase protein family, highlighting the complex evolutionary history of terpenoid enzymes.^[30,31]

However, biosynthetic pathways of terpenoid metabolites and the genetic foundation for terpene production in sponges remain largely unexplored. While multiple studies have concluded that, unlike other bioactive compounds, many terpenes are produced by the sponge hosts themselves rather than their symbionts, their exact origins may vary across sponge clades and terpene types.^[32–34] Parallel reports of terpenoid metabolites found in sponge-associated fungi across all sponge orders suggest that terpene biosynthesis in sponges may not exclusively be facilitated by the host only, underscoring the need for further research to determine their true origin.^[35–37]

Consequently, it remains unknown whether all terpene biosynthetic genes and pathways in sponges adhere to previously observed synthesis types or if other mechanisms, possibly independently evolved, are at play.^[34] Understanding mechanisms and pathways from the terrestrial realm is pivotal for identifying the genetic origins of bioactively potent but uncommon terpenoid metabolites (e.g., dictyoceratid sponge-specific marine scalarane sesterterpenes).^[38]

In this study, we analyze the genetic origins and possible genealogy of genes involved in the production of sponge-

Figure 3. Phylogenetic sub-tree ("FPPS" clade from Figure 4) simplifying the position and relationships of FPPS(-like) transcripts from sponges (red and blue: order level; green: species level), plants, fungi, and non-poriferan animals. Support values for Maximum Likelihood and Bayesian Inference (ML | BI), with bootstrap support < 50 indicated by dashed lines (—).

Figure 4. Simplified phylogenetic tree illustrating the phylogenetic positions and relationships of FPPS (see Figure 3), GGPPS (blue and green), GFPPS, DPS1 (orange), SDS/HPP (purple), and PPS (polyprenyl synthetase) of sponges and other taxa. Combined tree topology based on Maximum Likelihood (ML) and Bayesian Inference (BI) phylogenetic reconstructions. Support values displayed as "ML | BI"; unsupported values (bootstrap < 70, posterior probability < 0.95) indicated with "—".

derived terpenes, with a focus on dictyoceratid sponges. Our bioinformatic approach aims to identify potential genetic foundations for terpene biosynthesis using current transcriptomic and genomic data from various sponge orders, exemplary on sesterterpenes with yet unknown synthesis mechanisms. The findings of our research are intended to provide a foundational basis for future investigations into the genetic and biochemical pathways of terpenoid biosynthesis in sponges.

Results and Discussion

Molecular Phylogenetic Analyses

The concatenated amino acid alignment used for phylogenetic reconstructions consisted of 253 amino acid sequences (i.e., demosponge transcripts and NCBI GenBank sequences) and with an alignment length of 1305 molecular characters (see Open Data LMU <https://doi.org/10.5282/ubm/data.505>). The complete phylogenetic tree from ML and BI analyses (basis for Figures 3 and 4) can be found in the Supplementary Data (Supplementary Figure S1).

Presence of Prenyltransferases

Probing of the transcriptomic and genomic data for the different types of PT yielded high-scoring results for the respective HMM query profiles, however with partially overlapping hits due to the similarity in conserved sites characteristic for the polyprenyl synthases domain of these enzymes (see InterPro entry IPR033749). In the following sections different PTs subtrees will be described to illustrate phylogenetic similarities, differences, and the evolutionary history of PTs of sponges and other taxa (Figures 3 and 4, full tree in Supplementary Data Supplementary Figure S1).

Putative FPPS-like enzyme genes could be reliably identified in multiple transcripts for all studied sponges (Table 1), forming a monophylum sister to a plant-fungi and a non-poriferan animal clade (Figure 3). The sponge transcripts were further split into two major sub-clades comprising genes of the sponge orders Dictyoceratida and Dendroceratida (red clade, Figure 3), and all other sponge orders (blue clade, Figure 3), coinciding with the currently accepted phylogenetic relationships between Keratosa and other demosponges.^[39,40] The internal phylogeny of the Keratosa clade based on FPPS-like transcripts furthermore also matches the accepted phylogenetic relationships within Dictyoceratida and Dendroceratida.^[41,42] However, four transcripts of FPPS-like sequences of *Cymbastela concentrica* (Axinellida), *Dysidea avara* (Dictyoceratida), and *Spongia officinalis* (Dictyoceratida) (green in clade, Figure 3) also fall outside this clade and show higher affinity to the aforementioned plant and fungi genes.

In comparison, phylogenetic patterns of GGPPS differ from the reconstructed FPPS evolution. Here, *D. avara* and *Lendenfeldia chondrodes* (Dictyoceratida) are the only dictyoceratid sponges where this enzyme could be reliably detected. In

Table 1. Presence of different PTs in the studied sponge transcriptomes and genomes. Asterisk (*S. carteri* in order Scopalinida) indicates a currently controversial taxonomy. Legend: "X" = presence; "-" = absence.

Taxonomy			Present PTs			TCs
Order	Family	Species	FPPS	GGPPS	DPS1-like	SHC-like
Axinellida	Axinellidae	<i>Cymbastela concentrica</i>	X	X	-	X
Dendroceratida	Dendrillidae	<i>Dendrilla antarctica</i>	X	X	-	-
Dictyoceratida	Dysideidae	<i>Dysidea avara</i>	X	X	X	X
Dictyoceratida	Dysideidae	<i>Pleraplysilla spinifera</i>	X	-	X	-
Dictyoceratida	Irciniidae	<i>Sarcotragus fasciculatus</i>	X	-	X	-
Dictyoceratida	Thorectidae	<i>Lendenfeldia chondrodes</i>	X	X	X	-
Dictyoceratida	Thorectidae	<i>Phyllospongia foliascens</i>	X	-	X	-
Dictyoceratida	Spongiidae	<i>Spongia officinalis</i>	X	-	X	X
Dictyoceratida	Verticillitidae	<i>Vaceletia crypta</i>	X	-	X	X
Haplosclerida	Niphatidae	<i>Amphimedon queenslandica</i>	X	-	X	X
Haplosclerida	Petrosiidae	<i>Xestospongia testudinaria</i>	X	X	-	X
Poecilosclerida	Tedaniidae	<i>Tedania anhelans</i>	X	X	-	X
Scopalinida	Scopalinidae	<i>Scopalina</i> sp.	X	X	-	-
Scopalinida*	Scopalinidae*	<i>Stylissa carteri</i>	X	X	X	-
Spongillida	Spongillidae	<i>Ephydatia muelleri</i>	X	X	-	X
Tethyida	Tethyidae	<i>Tethya wilhelma</i>	X	X	-	X
Verongiida	Aplysinidae	<i>Aplysina aerophoba</i>	X	X	-	X

contrast, GGPPS is present in all other non-dictyoceratid sponge transcriptomes and genomes except *Xestospongia testudinaria* (Haplosclerida) (Table 1). Phylogenetically, GGPPS transcripts are divided in two distinct clades: one GGPPS clade, consisting mostly of non-dictyoceratid sponges, sister to enzymes from non-poriferan animals and fungi, respectively (blue clade, Figure 4). The second clade comprised plant derived GGPPS that also showed considerable similarity to respective enzyme genes from *L. chondrodes*, *D. avara* and *C. concentrica*, with a clade of (otherwise paraphyletic) bacterial GGPPS and further demersal sponge sequences from *X. testudinaria*, *Stylissa carteri* (Scopalinida), *D. antarctica* (Dendroceratida), and *Aplysina aerophoba* (Verongiida) as sister (green clade, Figure 4).

Queries for GFPPS did not recover hits analogous to genes present in other organisms. Instead, the highest scores in BLASTp searches were for decaprenyl-diphosphate synthase subunit 1 (DPS1), albeit with only around 50% sequence identity. All attempts to identify amino acid sequences with closer similarity to the targeted GFPPS failed to produce unambiguous results, typically returning hits for DPS1, or for GGPPS and FPPS when specificity was lacking. The DPS1-like sequences of sponges form a monophyletic clade, with *Amphimedon queenslandica* (Haplosclerida) and *S. carteri* genes being sister to otherwise exclusively dictyoceratid taxa. Similar to the FPPS-like transcripts described earlier, DPS1-like patterns parallel the accepted relationships between sponge orders, with the internal phylogeny of the multiple transcripts in the Dictyoceratida clade closely resembling their known phylogenetic affinities.^[42] DPS1-like transcripts were not present or expressed in any other non-dictyoceratid sponges, except in *A. queenslandica* and *S. carteri*, both of which display distinct

genetic differences to the dictyoceratid clade. Adjacent sister clades to these sponges were (in descending order) DPS1 of animal and fungal origin respectively (orange clade, Figure 4), a clade of sequences showing the highest identity to solanesyl-diphosphate synthase-like (SDS) or hexaprenyl pyrophosphate synthase-like (HPP) sequences from *C. concentrica* and *L. chondrodes* (purple clade, Figure 4), as well as a number of unspecific polyprenyl synthases (PPS) (Figure 4). GFPPS sequences of plant and bacterial origin were more similar to GGPPS of plants and animals/fungi, respectively (Figure 4).

Presence of Terpene Cyclases

Unexpectedly, the queries for common class I TCs of bacterial, plant or fungal origin also did not return any significant results, even when different variants of TC and TC-related protein domains and/or families were queried.

In an alternative approach to detect the potential presence of class II TCs of the common prokaryotic **squalene-hopene cyclase** (SHC) and eukaryotic **oxidosqualene cyclase** (OSC) types, we were able to identify a number of lanosterol synthase-like (or oxidosqualene synthase), cycloartenol synthase-like, or other SHC/OSC-related transcripts in almost all transcripts. Queries for OSC generally outscored SHC and recovered a number of seemingly partial OSC-like transcripts, particularly from the dictyoceratid specimens (Table 1). However, cross-referencing these partial hits against InterPro and BLAST databases recovered them with high likelihood as genes coding for geranylgeranyltransferase type II enzymes, not directly involved in terpene cyclization. As such, no pattern was

apparent from the observed distribution across sponge clades (not depicted) with respect to their taxonomy or known production of respective types of terpenes (Figure 1, Table 1).

Presence and Hypothetical Roles of Poriferan Prenyltransferases

In our endeavor to identify a potential genetic basis for terpene biosynthesis in sponges, we focused our search on the presence of different core intermediaries (PT for linear terpene substrate generation and TC for cyclisation to the final terpenoid product) that are known to be involved in the production of terpenoids in terrestrial and other marine organisms. We were able to identify the PT FPPS in all of the studied sponge transcriptomic and genomic resources used, often with multiple transcripts per species, being distinctly monophyletic in our molecular phylogenies (Figure 3).

FPPS, while being a core component in the generation of the C₁₅ substrate for sesquiterpenes and triterpenes, should, however, not be considered definitive proof for (complex) terpene biosynthesis, as its product, FPP, is also involved in the synthesis of other steroids and carotenoids.^[43,44] Despite the presence in multiple transcripts, the internal phylogeny of the monophyletic Dictyoceratida/Dendroceratida FPPS clade has considerably high resemblance to the currently accepted phylogenetic relationships within those sponge orders, contrary to the second Porifera FPPS sister clade, which appears not to be congruent.^[42] Only few FPPS-like sequences of *S. officinalis*, *C. concentrica* and *D. avara* show closer affinities to fungal and plant FPPS enzyme genes, while the majority of these transcripts group within their respective monophyletic sponge-FPPS clades. Consequently, symbiotic microorganisms (i.e., algae, fungi) are likely to be the source for transcripts with higher affinities to plants and fungi. However, the observed closer phylogenetic relationship between the Porifera and plant/fungi clades would suggest a Last Common Ancestor other than non-poriferan animals, however definite inferences are likely not possible based on highly variable datasets used (Figure 3).^[45,46]

GGPPS, the synthase enzyme for the linear C₂₀ substrate GGPP (Figure 3), can serve both as a basis for diterpenes, as

well as for carotenoids.^[47,48] We found transcripts for this gene to be less ubiquitous than FPPS, as sequences were not detected in transcripts of all studied sponges. Furthermore, we were unable to observe an unambiguous monophyly of GGPPS-like transcripts either (Figure 4). They are split between a clade of most non-dictyoceratid sponges with a closer relationship to clades of non-poriferan animals and fungi on the one hand, and GGPPS of plant origin (*L. chondrodes*, *C. concentrica*, *D. avara*) and (cyano)bacterial origin (*X. testudinaria*, *S. carteri*, *D. antarctica*, *A. aerophoba*) on the other hand (Figure 4). This may suggest differences in the origin of the respective gene transcripts from either sponge host or symbionts, as already hypothesized for FPPS earlier for two of the same species (*C. concentrica*, *D. avara*). Additionally, *S. carteri* and *A. aerophoba* also appear to have homologs in both GGPPS-like clades, despite terpene production not being reported in these species, and thus suggesting alternative functionalities of the respective genes in these clades.^[49,50] With *X. testudinaria*, *D. antarctica* and *L. chondrodes* only being represented in the plant-bacterial clade, a microbial symbiotic origin of the respective transcripts is likely (Figure 4). While Dendroceratida (*D. antarctica*) and Axinellida (*C. concentrica*) are known to be capable of diterpenoid metabolite production, this is yet unreported for the remaining sponges with GGPPS-like amino acid sequences in both the (non-poriferan) animal associated and plant-bacterial related clades. This either implies potential differences in the function of their GGPPS-like genes (e.g., capabilities for the carotenoid metabolite synthesis), or yet undetected presence of terpenoid compounds in the respective taxa. However, if Dictyoceratida or other sponges with GGPPS-like gene transcripts employed GGPP as substrate or precursor for diterpene and sesterterpene biosynthesis,^[48,51] the gene would be expected to be detectable in the majority of sponges with known potential for the synthesis of respective terpenoid metabolites (e.g., spongiane diterpenes in *S. officinalis*).^[52,53] Here, GGPPS appears to be absent or not expressed uniformly in the studied Dictyoceratida transcriptomes, implying alternative modes for diterpene and/or sesterterpene synthesis (Table 2), and consequently a potential evolutionary deviation from the conventional biosynthesis pathways known from most terrestrial terpenoid producers.^[54]

Table 2. Overview of Dictyoceratida and Dendroceratida species from which genetic data have been analyzed in this study, and their reported terpenoid metabolite diversity. Asterisk indicates the complete lack of biochemical studies and respective metabolite data (*Vaceletia crypta*).

Taxonomy			Terpenoids Reported		
Order	Family	Species	Sesquiterpenes	Diterpenes	Sesterterpenes
Dictyoceratida	Thorectidae	<i>Lendenfeldia chondrodes</i>	–	–	X
Dictyoceratida	Thorectidae	<i>Phyllospongia foliascens</i>	–	–	X
Dictyoceratida	Spongiidae	<i>Spongia officinalis</i>	X	X	X
Dictyoceratida	Irciniidae	<i>Sarcotragus fasciculatus</i>	X	–	X
Dictyoceratida	Dysideidae	<i>Dysidea avara</i>	X	–	–
Dictyoceratida	Dysideidae	<i>Pleraplysilla spinifera</i>	X	–	–
Dictyoceratida	Verticillitidae	<i>Vaceletia crypta</i>	–*	–*	–*
Dendroceratida	Dendrillidae	<i>Dendrilla antarctica</i>	–	X	–

Sesterterpenes are synthesized from a C₂₅ substrate (GFPP) condensed by GFPPS, which is subsequently cyclized into the final sesterterpenoid product by the respective sesterterpene synthases (TCs).^[51,55] Unlike GGPPS we were not able to identify this kind of PT in any of the Dictyoceratida or other sponge transcriptomes, based on HMM profiles compiled from GFPPS of bacterial, plant, fungal, and non-poriferan animal origin. The highest scoring results resembled DPS1, an enzyme known to facilitate the condensation of a linear C₅₀ backbone. DPS1 is usually associated with the elongation of the prenyl side chain of ubiquinone, so a different functionality in sponges cannot be excluded.^[56,57] The identified sponge DPS1-like homologs found in *S. carteri* and all sesterterpene-producing taxa in our dataset (i.e., Dictyoceratida and *A. queenslandica*) exhibit high similarity to the conserved aspartate-rich DDxxD motifs of DPS1, with approximately 50% sequence identity to comparable homologs in the BLASTp database (Figure 1, Figure 4).^[11] As the phylogenetic reconstruction of the DPS1-like genes follows currently accepted Dictyoceratida phylogenies,^[42] homology of these copies is plausible. Likewise, a joint origin of sponge DPS1-like and the metazoan DPS1 genes, due to their sister group relationship, appears to be likely and coincides with the previously discussed relationships of the majority of metazoan GGPPS genes (Figures 3 and 4). While duplication and neofunctionalization of ancestral DPS1-like genes for the sesterterpenoid biosynthetic process in sponges may be among plausible genealogical inferences based on our results, additional functional characterization of these candidate homologs in future studies would be required to verify their precise role in Dictyoceratida and other sponges.

Terpene Cyclase Genes in Sponges

The detected presence of different PT types, despite not always being direct evidence for terpenoid biosynthetic pathways, may constitute the foundation for the variety of known sponge-derived terpenoid metabolites as known to date. However, PTs only provide the linear substrate necessary for the synthesis of a terpene of respective length, while their cyclisation to the final terpenoid product is facilitated by TCs, which remain largely unknown from sponges. Facultative (i.e., activated) production of defensive bioactive compounds appears to be more common in sponges than initially thought, however, continuous production and storage for constant secondary metabolite levels still seems to be the standard for most Porifera.^[8,9,58] Induced enzymatic conversion of precursor molecules into active defensive agents was also demonstrated for sesterterpenes in *Luffariella variabilis* by Ettinger-Epstein et al.^[59] However, sustained biosynthesis and storage of terpenoid precursors and activating enzymes would also require corresponding genetic activity and constant expression in the transcriptome.^[9]

Unlike Burkhardt et al.^[28] and Scesa et al.^[29] for octocorals, Wei et al.^[60] for fungi, and Wilson et al.^[34] for sponges of the order Bubarida, we were not able to identify sponge TCs with the same methods and/or datasets in the analyzed tran-

scriptomic data, based on (curated) HMM profiles of potential TCs and related synthase domains. The conserved motifs for class I TCs (aspartate-rich motif DDxxD and NSE/DTE motif [N/D]xxx[S/T]xxxE), typically present in synthase enzymes for many terpenes in plants, bacteria and fungi, appear to be absent in all investigated sponges. However, conserved motifs of the TC protein family can also differ or be absent, suggesting an ancient and potentially complex evolutionary history, including the possibility of horizontal gene transfers.^[31] The findings of Wilson et al.^[34] illustrate this possibility in sponges, where a type I TC with an altered NSE/DTE motif (NDxxGxxxD) was identified. However, this motif was not present in any of the transcriptomes investigated in this study, suggesting it may be specific to sponges of the order Bubarida. Additionally, the unique motifs of the recently described class IB TS, a subtype of class I TCs, do not show similarity to any of our sponge transcripts or identified enzyme genes, making a common genealogical origin of these synthase genes unlikely.^[61]

Absence of characteristic conserved class I TC motifs suggests that sponge (sester)terpene biosynthesis may be facilitated by a class II TC variant instead, generally characterized by a catalytic central aspartate with a DxDD motif.^[2] The possible transformation of geranylarnesol, a linear sesterterpene, into a cyclic (scalarane) skeleton by the class II TCs SHC or OSC may represent another potential pathway for sesterterpene synthesis in dictyoceratid sponges.^[62-65] While we were able to identify SHC/OSC-like sequences in several of our studied sponge transcriptomes and genomes (Table 1), no conclusive genealogical pattern of the SHC transcripts, or function in terpene production, is obvious. The triterpenoid SHC/OSC products lanosterol (in animals and fungi) and cycloartenol (in plants) are important components in the cholesterol biosynthesis process, and as such SHC/OSC-like class II cyclase genes should be ubiquitous in sponges.^[66,67] Matches for the eukaryotic lanosterol synthase, evidencing sterol or triterpene production by the sponge host, were present in Haplosclerida and Axinellida (*A. queenslandica* and *C. concentrica*) transcriptomes, as well as in triterpene-less Tethyida, Poecilosclerida and Spongillida (*Tethya wilhelma*, *Tedania anhelans*, *Ephydatia muelleri*).^[11] The remaining SHC-like transcripts appear associated to organisms of bacterial origin, presumably symbionts, with a likewise unresolved function in triterpene or sesterterpene formation (see *D. avara*, *S. officinalis*, *V. crypta*, *A. aerophoba*, and *X. testudinaria*) (Table 1). The absence of OSC in almost half of the studied transcriptomes and genomes, particularly among Dictyoceratida, is puzzling given the importance of lanosterol in eukaryotic metabolism and previous evidence of OSC presence in sponges.^[67] Further investigations of class II terpene cyclases, using additional controlled transcriptomic and genomic datasets, are strongly encouraged to gain a better understanding of their role in terpenoid biosynthesis in (Dictyoceratida) sponges.

While our study employs comprehensive bioinformatic analyses to identify potential gene candidates involved in terpene biosynthesis in sponges, it is important to recognize the inherent limitations of this approach. Bioinformatic predictions, although powerful for hypothesis generation and preliminary identification, do not provide conclusive evidence of gene

function. The identified gene candidates require further experimental validation, including expression analysis, functional assays, and correlation with terpenoid production phenotypes, to definitively confirm their roles in terpene biosynthesis. Future research should focus on these experimental validations to fully elucidate the genetic and biochemical mechanisms underlying terpenoid biosynthesis in sponges.

Conclusions

In our effort to gain a basic understanding of the genetic foundations for terpene biosynthesis in Porifera, we were able to identify several components essential to the complex terpenoid biosynthetic pathway in sponges, particularly substrate synthase genes for various types of terpenoid metabolites. The recent discovery of highly specific terpene synthase genes in Bubarida sponges highlights the challenges of inferring complex genetic biosynthetic pathways, as similar genes could not be verified in the diverse poriferan transcriptomic data analyzed in this study. Consequently, despite the present efforts in sponge genomics our study reveals that more comprehensive genomic and experimental biochemical data from Dictyoceratida and other sponge orders is required to fully elucidate the widespread, but apparently highly complex process of terpene biosynthesis in sponges. Nevertheless, the results gained here indicate where targeted research is required to verify and decipher terpene production across various sponge orders.

Experimental Section

Sequence Acquisition and Assembly

Available raw transcriptomic paired-end reads for Dictyoceratida (7) and non-Dictyoceratida (2) were downloaded from the NCBI SRA database, processed and assembled with the TransPi v1.0.0 pipeline, with subsequent peptide characterization and translation using TransDecoder v5.5.0 (Supplementary Table S1).^[68,69] Due to the sister group relationship of the order Dendroceratida to Dictyoceratida within the subclass Keratosa, and the documented presence of spongiane diterpenes in *Dendrilla antarctica* (Dendroceratida), transcriptomic data of this species constitutes an important outgroup resource for understanding the biochemical evolutionary history of terpenoids in sponges, and Dictyoceratida in particular (Table 2).^[41,42,70] Further genomic and transcriptomic data of eight non-dictyoceratid sponges were downloaded from <https://spongebase.net/>.

Identification of Synthase Genes

For the identification of genes involved in the (sister)terpene biosynthetic process, Hidden Markov Model (HMM) profiles for the prenyltransferases FPP synthase (FPPS), GGPP synthase (GGPPS), and GFPP synthase (GFPPS) and TC classes I and II, were compiled from known genes in the NCBI database of animals, plants, bacteria, and fungi, as well as an additional TC HMM profile from a recent study on sesterterpene production in octocorals^[28] and Bubarida sponges^[34] (see Supplementary Tables S2a–f for details). Due to

their basic role in the terpenoid biosynthetic pathway (Scheme 1) and the scarcity of monoterpenoids in sponges, geranyl pyrophosphate synthase genes were not included in HMM searches. Further curated HMMs for a generic polyprenyl synthase domain (PF00348), different class I terpene synthase and domain entries (PF01397, PF03936, PF19086), and GGPPS (PTHR12001) were sourced from the Pfam and PANTHER databases.^[71,72] Additional HMMs for class II terpene cyclases of the squalene-hopene cyclase (SHC) (IPR006400) and squalene/oxidosqualene (OSC) types (TIGR01787.1) were obtained from the InterPro and NCBIfam databases.^[73,74]

Amino acid sequences derived from transcriptomic and genomic resources of 17 demosponge species (7 dictyoceratid, 10 non-dictyoceratid) were scanned for matches consistent with the prepared HMM profiles using HMMER v3.3.2, with the highest scoring transcripts (up to a inclusion threshold e-value of 10^{-10}) being aggregated and checked against blastp and InterProScan for more detailed categorisation of protein function and domain structure.^[75,76]

Phylogenetic Analysis

Identified sequences with putative TC (class I and II), FPPS, GGPPS, and GFPPS enzymes were aligned with MAFFT v1.4.0 as implemented Geneious Prime v2019.2.3, with subsequent phylogenetic analysis and tree building using the Geneious plugin version of FastTree v2.1.12 for preliminary trees, and RAXML v8.2.12 in raxmlGUI v2.0.10 as well as MrBayes v3.2.7 for maximum likelihood and Bayesian Inference (BI) analyses, respectively.^[77–81] Substitution model selection for phylogenetic tree reconstruction was performed with ModelTest-NG v0.1.7, suggesting LG+G4+F as the best fitting model for the phylogenetic analyses.^[82] BI analyses (four chains, default heat, sample frequency of every 500th generation) were terminated when markov chains converged as indicated by standard deviation of split frequencies < 0.05).

Author Contributions

AG and DE conceived and designed research. DE, AG, SV and GW performed molecular data generation and analysis. AG, MMR and OPT conducted biochemical interpretation of omics data. AG wrote the initial manuscript. All authors read, contributed to, and approved the manuscript.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available in the supplementary material of this article, and in the Open Data repository of the LMU (Open Data LMU) <https://doi.org/10.5282/ubm/data.505>

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